

Global PBL: Cross-cultural educational project for engineering students

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Abstract

Project-Based Learning (PBL) has been the active learning methodology used in a Cross-Cultural Engineering Project (CEP) that it is an educational project between Shibaura Institute of Technology (SIT) from Japan, NOVA School of Science and Technology (FCT NOVA), Universidade NOVA de Lisboa from Portugal and King Mongkut's University of Technology, Thonburi (KMUTT) from Thailand. This partnership occurred since July 2017, so three successful editions were achieved. The editions last nine days and were held in mid-July. The venue of the event was the Caparica Campus of the NOVA School of Science and Technology (FCT NOVA). The hard core of course participants are students from SIT (Japan), KMUTT (Thailand) and FCT NOVA (Portugal). Students from the Chulalongkorn University (Chula. Univ.) and Chiang Mai University (CMU) from Thailand and from University of Navarra of Spain had also participated in some editions of the event. More than 100 students, 20 teaching assistants and 10 teachers were involved on this global PBL on the three editions. The students were organized in interdisciplinary and international four or five teams of different graduate and undergraduate years, of different universities. Each team had to work in a contemporary problem related with Ecology, Energy, Eco-tourism, Community development among others. This paper presents the results of such experience, pointing out the benefits for the students and for the teachers. A discussion about the competencies acquired by the students is presented. Some challenges are also addressed.

Keywords: Engineering education, global PBL, cross-cultural experience, competencies, problem-solving skills.

1 Introduction

That we live in a global world could not be more true than today given the current pandemic situation. This epidemic started in a Chinese city and it spread in less than three months to the entire world, stopping it by the fear of this infectious. Since COVID-19 epidemic was declared as a pandemic at 11 of March 2020 (WHO, 2020), the efforts were united to face this pandemic and international multidisciplinary teams are working together to find a vaccine.

Nevertheless, the market globalization of goods, services and resources have been putting some challenges to the engineering education for a long time as reported by many authors and reports (Alves et al., 2013; ASME, 2012; Graham, 2012; King, 2012; Lucena et al., 2008; Matsumura & Tanabe, 2019; Melsa, 2007; National Academy of Engineering, 2005; UNESCO, 2010, 2015). Despite this fact, international engineering education systems and organizations continue working at different rhythms and under different curricular structures (Alves et al., 2013; Lucena et al., 2008). To know and discuss these differences it is important to bring engineering educators from different countries to work together in doing common research (Borrego & Bernhard, 2011; Lima et al., 2019; Mesquita et al., 2019) or promoting common educational cross-cultural projects.

One such educational project is the Cross-Cultural Engineering Project (CEP) that is based on Project-Based Learning (Kongwat et al., 2020; Navas, 2017, 2018; Yamashita & Hasegawa, 2020) and it is the focus of this paper. This project is undertaken by three universities from Portugal, Japan and Thailand. It provides a rich and

meaningful experience for teachers and, most important, students. This paper discusses such benefits and challenges for teachers and students. Mainly it discusses what competencies students acquire when involved in such global PBL environment (gPBL).

Project-Based Learning (PBL) is, by their own nature and roots (Dewey, 1916; Kilpatrick, 1918), a suitable environment to promote key competencies referred by Council of the European Union (2018) as lifelong learning competencies. These are: 1) Literacy; 2) Multilingual; 3) Mathematical, science, technology and engineering; 4) Digital; 5) Personal, social and learning to learn; 6) Citizenship; 7) Entrepreneurship and; 8) Cultural awareness and expression (2018, p. 15). These contribute equally to a successful life in society, can be applied in many different contexts and in a variety of combinations and are supportive to each other, overlapping in some situations.

Competencies implies knowledge (facts and figures, concepts, ideas and theories which are already established and support the understanding of a certain area or subject); skills (ability and capacity to carry out processes and use the existing knowledge to achieve results) and attitudes (disposition and mind-sets to act or react to ideas, persons or situations) (Council of the European Union, 2018; Rychen & Salganik, 2000). These key competences embed critical thinking, problem solving, teamwork, communication and negotiation skills, analytical skills, creativity, and intercultural skills that are the most reported for the 21st century (Kang, 2019; The Economist, 2015; UNESCO, 2016; World Economic Forum, 2015).

Another important definition of competency is presented in Matsumura and Tanabe (2019) work. Competency is an action tendency and decision-making style derived from one's experience that is related to the ability to bring out the best in oneself and others. It involves the ability to behave and act in a way that promotes mutual communication with others as a working adult in society. Three main skills support this competency definition: teamwork (relating and collaborating with others and team management); personal (self-control, self-confidence and behavior control) and problem-solving (problem identification, planning and implementing solutions). Matsumura and Tanabe (2019) discussed how education system in Japan has been assessing generic skills which they divide in two aspects: literacy (knowledge application ability) and competency (action/decision making tendency). These generic skills are assessed using the Progress Report on Generic Skills (PROG). PROG has been also used to measure the achievement of international PBL referred above, the CEP.

By developing an open-ended project in a PBL context, students collaborate in teams and organize themselves to pursuit project objectives concretized in deliverables. To achieve this, these teams manage resources, time and cost, accomplishing tasks and milestones and solving problems. By actively participating on these activities and they will acquire the competencies referred. PBL has been implemented in many universities around the world (Alves & Leão, 2015; Davies et al., 2011; Guerra et al., 2017; Jollands et al., 2012; Kokotsaki et al., 2016; Lima et al., 2017; Mills & Treagust, 2003; Pereira & Barreto, 2016; Powell & Weenk, 2003), from the engineering first years (Alves et al., 2019; Lima et al., 2007) to final years in projects with companies (Dinis-Carvalho et al., 2017; Lima et al., 2015). Nevertheless, cross-cultural PBL experiences as well as cultural dimension impact on PBL are more difficult to find (Mohd-yusof et al., 2013).

PBL is also an active learning methodology suitable to provide the needed competences to pursuit a Society 5.0 (Ferreira & Serpa, 2018; Keidanren, 2018; Komiyama & Yamada, 2018; Pereira et al., 2020). According to a publication in the World Economic Forum meeting *"People will be expected to exercise rich imaginations to identify a variety of needs and challenges scattered across society and the scenarios to solve them, as well as creativity to realize such solutions by using digital technologies and data. Society 5.0 will be an Imagination Society, where digital transformation combines with the creativity of diverse people to bring about "problem solving" and "value creation" that lead us to sustainable development. It is a concept that can contribute to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted by the United Nations."* (Nakanishi, 2019). This concept, originated from Japan, is a strategy to deal with the impact of an ageing population (Pereira et al., 2020).

This paper is divided in five sections. The first section presents a brief background on the themes of the research presented in this paper and the objectives. The second section presents the research methodology. Section

three introduces the context and gPBL teams organization. The results are presented in the section four. Lastly, section fifth draws some concluding remarks.

2 Research methodology

The defined objectives for the paper are fulfilled by presenting the teams outcomes related with learning outcomes established for the gPBL. The key competences developed by the students are discussed at the light of the outcomes results and teachers observations and experience. For the study presented in this paper, it was used the skills embed in the key competences proposed by the Council Recommendation on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning (Council of the European Union, 2018), as referred in section 1.

It is important to notice that CEP sponsors have done previous researches and measurements of this gPBL using the PROG measurement system. Comparison of gPBL attendant and non-attendant Japanese students showed very positive results to the attendees, mainly, to their development of teamwork skills (relating with others and team management) and personal skills (self-control) (Matsumura & Tanabe, 2019).

3 Global PBL context and organization

Since July 2017, three editions of Global PBL have been held at NOVA School of Science and Technology (FCT NOVA), University NOVA of Lisbon. All editions were organized by Shibaura Institute of Technology (SIT) from Japan, FCT NOVA from Portugal and King Mongkut's University of Technology, Thonburi (KMUTT) from Thailand (Figure 1). The CEP is based on Global Project Based Learning through the problem solving experience (Navas, 2017).

Figure 1. Location of the three universities involved in the gPBL

3.1 Context

The venue of the event in the three editions discussed in this paper is the Caparica Campus of the NOVA School of Science and Technology (FCT NOVA), University NOVA of Lisbon. The hard core of course participants are students from SIT (Japan-JP), KMUTT (Thailand) and FCT NOVA (Portugal-PT). Students from the Chulalongkorn University (Chula. Univ.) of Thailand, from the Chiang Mai University (CMU) of Thailand (TH) and from University of Navarra of Spain (SP) have also participated in some editions of the event. The editions last nine days and are held in mid-July. The Table 1 presents the numbers for the three editions.

Table 1. Characterization of the three last editions

	Event days	No. students	Number of groups	Teaching assistants	Professors
2017	11-19 July	17	3	3 (PT, JP, TH)	4 (PT, JP, TH)
2018	10-18 July	28	5	7 (PT, JP, TH)	4 (PT, JP, TH)
2019	9-17 July	37	6	7 (PT, JP, TH)	5 (PT, JP, TH)

All activities are taught and directed by Professors and Teaching Assistants (TA). Professors act as an assumed investor to project. They make various kinds of comments and suggestions in the Design Review (DR). TAs advise the teams to coordinate with the local staff, to support the management of teams. Comments from various points of view among lecturers are allowed. Basic stance is to pay respect to students' ideas and opinions. The lecturers should not force the students to follow their comments (Navas, 2018).

It is expected that students learn in practice to work with the several methodologies such as Attractive Quality, Kano Model, Kando Quality, Quality Function Deployment (QFD), TRIZ, Lean A3, etc. At the end of the Cross-cultural Educational Project (CEP), students should be able to do:

- Goal setting
- Assessment planning
- Budget planning
- Schedule planning for activities

The CEP enables students:

- To acquire the synthetic problem solving capability to be internationally attractive
- To acquire concepts and technologies on "Systems thinking", "Systems Method (Engineering Method)", and "Systems Management (Project Management)"
- To acquire a capability of work as a member of an international and/or interdisciplinary team

The assessment components are:

1. Design review result
 - Teamwork
 - Personal
 - Problem-solving
2. Final Presentation result
 - Outcome assessment considering:
 - Work in multi-culture and interdisciplinary team
 - Leadership
 - System thinking and engineering

These assessments are measured using the PROG system scales. It is used an assessment grid where components 1 and 2 are ranked. The CEP staff team, normally, set-up awards to be assigned to the first three places.

3.2 PBL teams organization

All teams are composed five to six graduate students and undergraduate students. Each team is made up of the students from several countries and universities. Students have to communicate in English, even if they use freely various devices and services, such as electronic dictionaries, smartphones and the Internet. Teams were formed based on their nationalities and on the questionnaire for team forming, which was prepared by professors and TAs. The Figure 2 illustrates the practical process of the Global PBL.

Figure 2 – Practical Process for Global PBL

In Global PBL, unexpected problems faced by people very frequently in the real world, will be induced by intention as an improvisation education (Navas, 2017; Yamashita & Hasegawa, 2020). This “Oh my God” experience should trigger the improvement of competency and it is detailed explained in Yamashita and Hasegawa (2020). Each team is requested to reconstruct the process of solving the problems by rescheduling. Improvisation education is performed to obtain creatively adaptation skill to unexpected changes in a project. All through the project, students are expected not only to make a plan but also make a design, implementation and a fieldwork about a pre-defined theme.

Some keywords are referred for setting the theme: Ecology, Energy, Eco-tourism, Community development, Service, Mobility, Welfare and medical system, Disaster prevention, Multi-language communication, User experience, Innovation, Education system, Global leadership, Unexamined Patent, Others (student's idea). As an examples, the last year the themes of the teams were: Wearable transportation IC system, Train safety; Fun time Fun Life, Ocean Waste Removal and Alternatives to air conditioning on cars.

The definition of the problem and its solution is made using various methods, thinking processes and systematic communication tools, such as Brainstorming, KJ Method, Mind map, etc.

4 Results

This section presents some results of competencies developed by gPBL attendees in the teachers opinion and experience. These are obtained by matching teams outcomes results (design review and final presentation) with the competencies definition provided in section 1 and some PROG results retrieved pre-, during and post gPBL (Matsumura & Tanabe, 2019). Additionally, these were supported by the observations and experience of the CEP staff coordination team. Table 2 presents such results through some evidences and examples.

Table 2. Characterization of the three editions

Competencies	Knowledge	Skills	Attitudes
Literacy	New methodologies	New technical and social skills	Greater confidence and security in knowledge
Multilingual	Improved knowledge of English	Understanding conversations and speaking skills in English.	Initiative to communicate with foreign partners

Mathematical, science, technology and engineering	Attractive Quality, Kano Model, Kando Quality, QFD, TRIZ, Lean A3, Idea Creation Support System; System Thinking and Engineering	Problem-solving, ideas generation, creativity, apply engineering methodologies to solve interdisciplinary problem	Proactivity, explore other tools, creativity
Digital	Be aware of new tools to communicate	Digital tools use (e.g. videos)	Initiative to use different tools, to share information
Personal, social and learning to learn	Plan a project and activities, plan, distribute individual and team tasks, establish a contact with a company, public presentation	Negotiate and solve conflicts, initiative to present a topic and answer to questions	Initiative to develop prototypes; communicate, how to act in public, friendship culture, backup by encouraging members when they are negative
Citizenship	Informal aspects of citizenship, consider and accept different values	Transmit country values	Feeling of national pride and wanting to transmit national values to foreign partners
Entrepreneurship	Manage a project with a company and collaborate in a multidisciplinary team	Build the products prototypes, mobilize resources; leadership	Stimulus and motivation to make the project, create a positive atmosphere for the team
Cultural awareness and expression	Culture from other countries, understand the differences and respect them	Work in multicultural teams and environments	Culture exchange, motivational change

If the knowledge could be best learned through traditional classes and this project could bring some novelties that will need to be practiced in the professional work, the skills and attitudes are mostly developed through projects and others active learning methodologies (Alves et al., 2018; Council of the European Union, 2018). Particularly, the skills and attitudes related to cultural issues are burst in this kind of project.

5 Conclusions

This paper discussed the competencies developed by students in gPBL environment to the light of the life-long learning key competences recommended by European Council. Some of these are coincident with generic skills assessed by PROG measurement system in Japan. Mainly, the teamwork, personal and problem-solving framed as competency for PROG system have been ranked with high scores. Nevertheless, more than these are obtained, as the examples and evidences presented in Table 2 revealed. The challenges to work in a different country in a multidisciplinary team could be "simulated" in this gPBL bringing many benefits, being the main one the preparation of better professionals capable to work in a global work market. Even for the teachers this is a challenge, that when surpassed becomes a great benefit. Nevertheless, it is of general opinion that the difficulties were more related to the theme selection than with cultural issues. The awareness of the "different" cultures gave to the students an openness mind-set, which contribute to the best fit integration and help each other understanding. It would be important as future work to deepen these, probably, by doing a questionnaire or using a PROG similar measurement system to assess the students competencies that attended to this gPBL.

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